

The Effect Of Skills And Integrity On Employee Performance At Pt. Pln Indonesia Power Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit Tapanuli Tengah Regency

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Abstrak: *This study aims to determine the influence of Skills and Integrity on employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power, Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit, Central Tapanuli Regency. This study employed a quantitative method with a descriptive approach. The sample consisted of employees at PT. PLN Indonesia Power, Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit, Central Tapanuli Regency, with a questionnaire distributed to 59 respondents. The t-test results revealed that the calculated t-value for Skills was $4.910 > t\text{-table } 2.00324$ with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$, and for Integrity was $3.654 > t\text{-table } 2.00324$ with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$. The F-test results show a calculated F-value of $54.046 > F\text{-table } 3.16$, with a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. Thus, Skills and Integrity simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.*

Keywords: *Skills, Integrity, and Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

The Labuhan Angin Power Plant was established and began commercial operations in 2009. Unit 1 began operating on November 7, 2009, while Unit 2 began operating on April 21, 2009. The inauguration of the Labuhan Angin Power Plant was carried out on January 28, 2010, by President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono. The Labuhan Angin Power Plant operates to supply electricity needs in the North Sumatra Interconnection System (Sumbagut). This power plant has a capacity of 2x115 MW and is operated by PT PLN Indonesia Power Service.

As a company, the target or objective of the Labuhan Angin Power Plant is to strengthen the electricity supply in the North Sumatra system. This power plant will distribute electricity through a 150 kV High Voltage Transmission Line (SUTT) to the Sibolga Main Substation. The Labuhan Angin Power Plant has a capacity of 2x115 MW, which means its total capacity is 230 MW. This achievement would not be possible without employees possessing specialized skills.

Skills are the ability to do something well, quickly, and accurately, both physically and mentally. Skills include dexterity, agility, and the ability to complete tasks easily and carefully. A person's work performance is highly dependent on their skills. The skills that a

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person possesses can increase labor productivity, which will greatly benefit the workforce. Good skills always provide benefits for maintaining the company's survival.

In reality, not all employees have good skills in their field of work, especially skills in terms of their perception of their work and skills in self-control (attitude, emotions, and motivation at work). Employees must be ready to face changes in the business environment of the power generation industry. Incompetence in facing these changes prevents employees from contributing effectively to the progress of the power plant.

In a study conducted by Neni Marlina (2018), the results show that there is an influence of skills on the performance of employees at PT. Bank Sumsel Syariah Palembang. Employees who are not skilled in facing competition from changes in the business environment cannot contribute better to their performance and to the progress of the company. If this happens, the company's performance will not experience significant progress and will not be able to compete with other companies.

Every employee must improve their skills through various training programs that support the development of abilities in to improve performance. Relevant training will help an employee to remember and improve their capacity as an employee in solving problems experienced by the company. Good skills include technical abilities relevant to the field of work or interests, as well as non-technical skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem solving. These skills need to be continuously honed through practice, learning, and experience.

In addition to skills, employee performance is also influenced by integrity. Integrity is a concept that refers to unity, wholeness, and consistency within a person, which reflects actions and behaviors that are in line with their beliefs, code of ethics, and moral principles. In other words, integrity is about how a person acts in accordance with what they say and believe, demonstrating honesty, responsibility, and moral integrity.

The integrity of an employee is very much needed in a company. Without integrity, an employee will live without principles, trust, and responsibility, which will affect their performance. Mujiagus Pranotoh (2019) in his research stated that integrity and loyalty have a significant positive effect on employee performance at PT. Latexindo Toba Perkasa Binjai. Thus, integrity can have an impact on personal and social life, making a person less trustworthy and difficult to build healthy relationships. In the work environment, a lack of integrity can damage reputation, erode trust, and hinder career growth.

Therefore, it is necessary to build employee integrity at work. In order to foster and realize employee integrity, a continuous process must be undertaken, involving honesty, consistency, responsibility, and keeping promises. Important steps include upholding the values you believe in, taking responsibility for your actions, having the courage to say 'no' to unethical things, and always acting honestly and fairly.

Performance is the result of work or achievements made by an individual, a group, or an organization in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, usually measured based on certain standards and within a certain period of time. Mangkunegara (2017:67) states that "Performance (work achievement) is the qualitative and quantitative result of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them." Employee performance is a description of the achievement of an

employee's work in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Employee performance is considered good when an employee is able to complete their tasks and responsibilities effectively and efficiently, in accordance with established standards, and contributes positively to the achievement of organizational goals. This includes good work quality, timeliness in completing tasks, the ability to work together, and initiative at work.

From preliminary research conducted by researchers, employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power's Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit in Central Tapanuli Regency has not been maximized. Researchers observed that the suboptimal performance of employees was due to aspects of employee skills and integrity that were not yet categorized as good. In terms of skills, there are still employees who need to improve their work abilities. The skills of some employees are currently considered outdated and need to be refreshed and updated in the work system. Then, related to the aspect of integrity, there are still employees who feel that the positions and responsibilities given to them are not in line with their desires and wishes, so these employees do not work effectively and efficiently.

Based on the above phenomena and issues, the author is interested in conducting a study entitled *The Influence of Skills and Integrity on Employee Performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power, Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit, Central Tapanuli Regency.*

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative method with a descriptive approach to test specific hypotheses. The population and sample include all 26 employees of the Sibolga City Cooperatives, SMEs, and Manpower Office (total sampling/saturated sampling). Primary data were gathered through structured interviews and Likert-scale questionnaires. Statistical analysis includes instrument validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests (normality and heteroscedasticity), and multiple linear regression analysis.

The type of data used is research data in the form of objects or items collected through observation. The data sources collected are primary data obtained directly from respondents and direct observations during the research. This study also uses secondary data in the form of records, reports, and archives from the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office and other sources.

Data collection techniques are methods used to obtain the data needed in a study using specific tools. According to Sugiyono (2017:137), "Data collection can be carried out in various *settings*, from various sources, and in various ways." In terms of the method or technique of data collection (), the data collection technique used in this study was as follows:

- a. Literature Study, which involves studying various reading sources closely related to the research problem, both in the form of scientific books and laws and regulations.
- b. Field Study, which involves collecting data directly from the research location by:
- c. Observation is the process of obtaining first-hand data and information by conducting observations.

- d. Documentation, which is a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, written numbers and images in the form of reports and information that can support the research.
- e. Interviews, which are a method of collecting data by conducting face-to-face interviews with parties who can provide information about supervision, career development, and work ethic, which are factors in the research.
- f. Questionnaires, which are a data collection technique that involves submitting written questions to respondents, who must also answer in writing.

The data analysis technique in this study is adapted to quantitative research methods, emphasizing hypothesis testing through statistical analysis. The data analysis techniques used in this study are: research instrument testing, classical assumption testing, determination testing, simple linear regression testing, and hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Research Instrument Test

Validation Test of the variables of Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation.

The results of the validity test of the variables of Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation can be seen in the table.

Table 1. Results of the Validity Test of the Variables of Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation

Item No.	$r_{\text{calculated}}$	r_{critical}	Conclusion
Variable X1 (Supervision)			
Item 1	.595	0.30	Valid
Item 2	.518	0.30	Valid
Item 3	.692	0.30	Valid
Item 4	.639	0.30	Valid
Item 5	.444	0.30	Valid
Item 6	.673	0.30	Valid
Item 7	.576	0.30	Valid
Item 8	.593	0.30	Valid
Item 9	.465	0.30	Valid
Item 10	.595	0.30	Valid
Variable X2 (Career Development)			
Item 1	.676	0.30	Valid
Item 2	.791	0.30	Valid
Item 3	.362	0.30	Valid
Item 4	.598	0.30	Valid
Item 5	.750	0.30	Valid
Item 6	.739	0.30	Valid
Item 7	.830	0.30	Valid
Item 8	.407	0.30	Valid
Item 9	.598	0.30	Valid

Item 10	.750	0.30	Valid
Variable Y (Work Motivation)			
Item 1	.690	0.30	Valid
Item 2	.684	0.30	Valid
Item 3	.570	0.30	Valid
Item 4	.559	0.30	Valid
Item 5	.504	0.30	Valid
Item 6	.783	0.30	Valid
Item 7	.732	0.30	Valid
Item 8	.606	0.30	Valid
Item 9	.532	0.30	Valid
Item 10	.717	0.30	Valid

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on Table 1, it can be concluded that all questionnaire items for the research variables, namely Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation, show values greater than 0.30. Thus, all items for the variables of Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation above are declared valid and meet the requirements as measurement tools in this study.

Reliability Test of the Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation Variables.

Table 2. Results of the Reliability Test for the variables of Supervision, Career Development, and Employee Work Motivation

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
1	Supervision	0.858	Reliable
2	Career Development	0.902	Reliable
3	Work Ethic	0.891	Reliable

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on the results of the reliability test of the research instrument in Table 2, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* value of each item in each variable is > 0.60 and is declared reliable.

Normality Test

Table 3. Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test for Supervision, Career Development, and Work Motivation Variables
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		26
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.000000
	Std. Deviation	20.51079517

Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.148	
	Positive	.112	
	Negative	-.148	
Test Statistic		.148	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		.146	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^d	Sig.	.145	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.136
		Upper Bound	.154

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. Lilliefors' method based on 10,000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 2,000,000.

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

From the table above, it can be seen that Asymp. Sig is 0.146 > probability 0.05 and the Kolmogorov Smirnov Z value is 0.148 < the Z value for sig 5% which is 1.97, meaning that both variable data are normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: SPSS 27 Processing Results

Figure 1. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Based on the figure above, the points are scattered randomly and spread both above and below zero on the Y-axis, so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

Coefficient of Determination

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Output Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.872 ^a	.760	.739	21.38398

a. Predictors: (Constant), Career Development, Supervision

b. Dependent Variable: Work Motivation

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on Table 4 in the R Square column, it can be concluded that the coefficient of determination is 0.760 or 76%. This figure explains that 76% of the variation in the work motivation of employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office can be explained by the variables of supervision and career development together, while the remaining 24% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. In other words, 76% of employee work motivation at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower

Office is influenced by the factors of Supervision and Career Development at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office, while the remaining 24% is influenced by other factors not examined by the author in this study, such as Organizational Culture, Leadership, Motivation, Communication, Work Environment, Delegation of Authority, and so on.

Simple Linear Regression

Table 5. Regression Coefficient Output and T-Test (Hypothesis Test) Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	23,297	41,977		.555	.584		
Supervision	.308	.119	.325	2,577	.017	.657	1,523
Career development	.612	.121	.641	5,079	.000	.657	1,523

a. Dependent Variable: Work Ethic

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

From Table 5 above, the regression equation $Y = 23.297 + 0.308X_1 + 0.612X_2$ is obtained, which can be interpreted as follows:

- Constant (23.297): If supervision and career development are absent (zero), the baseline employee work motivation remains at 23.297 units.
- Supervision (X_1): A coefficient of 0.308 indicates that better supervision directly increases work motivation.
- Career Development (X_2): A coefficient of 0.612 indicates that improved career opportunities significantly boost employee enthusiasm..

Hypothesis Test (F Test)

The F Test (Anova Test) was conducted to determine or explain whether Supervision and Career Development have a simultaneous effect on Employee Motivation at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office, the results of which can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. F Test Results (Anova Test)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	33271.144	2	16,635.572	36,380	.001 ^b
Residual	10,517.318	23	457,275		
Total	43,788.462	25			

a. Dependent Variable: Work Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Career Development, Supervision

Source: Research Results, 2025 (Processed Data)

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the influence of Supervision and Career Development together or simultaneously on the Work Motivation of employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office is as follows:

- From the results of conventional testing at a significance level of 0.05 with numerator df = 2 and denominator df = 23 (obtained from the results of df, $(n-k-1) = (26-2-1) = 23$, it is known that the table F = 3.42 and the calculated F = 36.380. Because F calculated > F table, it can be said that Supervision and Career Development have a positive effect on the Work Ethic of employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office.

From the results of testing using SPSS, namely by looking at the significance probability (P-value) = 0.001, which is smaller than 0.05, it can be said that Supervision and Career Development have a significant effect on the Work Ethic of employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Skills on Employee Performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Generation Business Unit Labuhan Angin, Tapanuli Tengah Regency

Based on the research results, it shows that the influence of skills on employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Generation Business Unit Labuhan Angin, Tapanuli Tengah Regency, which has been conducted, there is a significant influence of skills on employee performance. The t-test results show that the calculated t value is greater than the table t value ($4.910 > 2.00324$) with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$, therefore H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that skills have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit in Tapanuli Tengah Regency. Thus, the proposed hypothesis is proven and accepted as true.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Didit Darmawan and Rahayu Mardikaningsih (2021). In their study entitled The Influence of Interpersonal Skills, Work Experience, Integrity, and Work Commitment on the Performance of Agricultural Extension Workers, the results showed that interpersonal skills play a significant role in the performance of Agricultural Extension Workers.

The Influence of Integrity on Employee Performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit, Tapanuli Tengah Regency

Based on the research results, it was found that integrity has a significant influence on employee performance at PT PLN Indonesia Power UBP Labuhan Angin. The T-test results show that the calculated t-value $>$ t-table ($3.654 > 2.00324$) with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the proposed hypothesis that integrity has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT PLN Indonesia Power UBP Labuhan Angin is proven and accepted. thus, the proposed hypothesis is proven and accepted as true.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Didit Darmawan and Rahayu Mardikaningsih (2021). In their study entitled The Influence of Interpersonal Skills, Work Experience, Integrity, and Work Commitment on the Performance of Agricultural Extension Workers, the results showed that integrity has a significant effect on the performance of extension workers. It is also consistent with previous research conducted by Fajar Oktavianus Manao (2023). In his study entitled The Influence of Integrity and Communication on Employee Performance at the Fanayama Sub-District Office in South Nias Regency. His research results show that integrity (XI) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y) at the Fanayama Sub-District Office in South Nias Regency.

The Influence of Skills and Integrity on Employee Performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit, Central Tapanuli Regency.

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the influence of skills and integrity on employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power's Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit in Central Tapanuli Regency has been proven that skills and integrity have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power's Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit in Central Tapanuli Regency. This result can be seen from the F table value = 3.16 and the F count value = 54.046. Since the calculated F value is greater than the table F value with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that the hypothesis that skills and integrity have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT. PLN Indonesia Power Labuhan Angin Power Plant Business Unit in Tapanuli Tengah Regency is proven and accepted as true.

CONCLUSION

From the research that has been conducted and based on the results described in the previous chapter, the researcher can provide the following conclusions and suggestions: Based on the analysis of the Coefficient of Determination obtained at 0.760, this means that the variation in the dependent variable of employee work motivation (Variable Y) is 76% determined by Supervision and Career Development simultaneously, and the remaining 24% is determined by other factors not discussed in this study, such as Organizational Culture, Leadership, Motivation, Communication, Work Environment, Delegation of Authority, and so on. The results of testing the research hypothesis prove that the Supervision variable has an effect on employee Work Ethic. This result can be seen from the t-table value = 2.06866 and t-count = 2.577. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.017 < 0.05$, it can be said that Supervision has a positive and significant effect on employee Work Ethic. Thus, the hypothesis stating that Supervision has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Work Motivation of Employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office is proven and accepted. The results of testing this research hypothesis prove that the Career Development variable affects employee work motivation. This result can be seen from the t-table value = 2.06866 and t-count = 5.079. Because t-count > t-table with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$, it can be said that Career Development has a positive and significant effect on employee morale. Thus, the hypothesis stating that Career Development has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Work Motivation of employees at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office is proven and acceptable. The results of testing this research hypothesis prove that the variables of Supervision and Career Development affect employee Work Motivation. This result can be seen from the F table value = 3.42 and F count = . Because F count > F table with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$, it can be said that Supervision and Career Development have a positive and significant effect on employee morale at the Sibolga City SME and Manpower Cooperative Office. Thus, the hypothesis stating that Supervision and Career Development have a positive and significant effect on employee morale at the Sibolga City Cooperative, SME, and Manpower Office is proven and accepted.

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